

ELECTRONIC LAB NOTEBOOKS - EARLY RESEARCH PRACTICE IN TEACHING

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Abstract

Anyone who has his academic background in a natural science subject is already familiar with it: the lab notebook. Even in times of digitization, the most common type of laboratory documentation can still be found on paper. But what happens to these books when they are full? When the researcher changes the workgroup? Or if there simply is no longer a contact person for this lab notebook? Deciphering handwriting is not always the easiest task for man and machine, much of the collected knowledge is lost, many experiments are made over and over again instead of focusing on innovation. All this can be achieved with the use of an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN).

Electronic lab notebooks are a perfect tool to work collaboratively in the lab. In doing so, they are in no way inferior to their ancestor in paper form: general principles of scientific work are pursued (at the appropriate time the work follows the existing, generally recognized professional standards ("lege artis", state of the art), results are documented and the own outcome can be consistently challenged). All work steps are logged on the basis of a data record, data deletion is not possible, immutability is guaranteed by timestamps and all this is digitally searchable across different experiments. With the right archiving overtime in the laboratory can be prevented and the organizational structure in the daily routine is standardized, resulting in a better quality and more transparent collaborative work can be.

We at the Heinrich-Heine-University in Duesseldorf have a laboratory share of 70% within the new buildings of the natural sciences, and we have found out in talks with scientists that you have to start there already.

The laboratories must be equipped with appropriate technology, the interfaces of laboratory equipment to the ELN must be established, and the phrase "bring your own device", which is commonly used today, can make it possible for everyone to participate in the conversion to electronic laboratory work. It is also difficult to positively influence the willingness of scientists to move away from their usual paper book to the electronic version. Young scientists are the point at which to start, preferably at the beginning of the curriculum.

With the goal of creating a cultural change towards electronic laboratory books, for example, in the field of biology master students of the course "Cellular and molecular analysis of brain function" can be introduced into the laboratory notebook software with video tutorials and the first steps in fluorometric imaging can be learned under laboratory conditions, i.e. how data should be generated and evaluated. In close cooperation with the teachers, the lab book can be optimized for teaching purposes, and the integration of this subject area offers real added value for students. This is how young scientists learn how to use electronic lab books at an early stage and will continue to apply these new standards in research.

But also in other subjects, such as medicine, physics, chemistry, pharmacy, psychology and engineering can be set early in teaching to establish standards in research. As a building block to strengthen data and information literacy, the use of ELN in the natural sciences can be seen in the humanities and social sciences analogous to the use of e-portfolio systems such as Mahara.

Keywords: ELN, Lab Notebook, STEM, Digitization, research practice, medicine, physics, chemistry, pharmacy, psychology, engineering

1 INTRODUCTION

In Germany, a new principle of operation is currently being developed in the area of the structure and organization of laboratory work: documentation using electronic laboratory notebooks (ELN). Researchers have a colorful mix of data such as graphic files, formulas, spreadsheets or microscopy files. All this data should be digitally recorded together with important notes and arranged according to their own standards, but should also be completely searchable. This research data must also be available after the researcher has left the project and must not fall victim to an unwanted laboratory accident. According to experience researchers strive for a central storage of their data, be it the (partly long) storage of the raw data or the group organization by using calendars, maintaining a database for a better overview over inventories or also the pre-structured documentation of the laboratory work. Here it is important for the later proof obligation to be able to record a certain status by timestamp.

Many laboratory software started as part of a Laboratory Information and Management System (LIMS) and later was split into a separate structure. Unfortunately, the current equipment of most laboratories often includes a paper laboratory book as the only documentation. Even electronic documentation sources, such as tables or graphics, are printed and glued. This complete work of art of the documentation, see "Fig. 1", must be borrowed and leafed through when information is needed. When a book is full, it must be kept safe (or often ends up in a box at the researcher's home) and there is no backup copy. Research is often duplicated and threefold because of the difficulty in finding information. Handwritten notes in particular have faded after 20 years and are hardly legible.

Figure 1. Pen & Paper & Print Labbook[1]

2 METHODOLOGY

At the Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf (HHU) there is regular consultation and support of researchers in the field of research data management (RDM). In addition to assistance with the application, we also offer support through various RDM tools, including two different electronic lab books.

The Center for Information and Media Technology of HHU (ZIM) has been providing researchers with the commercial ELN "labfolder" in their own hosting variant for several years. In the course of the cooperation project "FoDaKo" funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), a cooperation of three North Rhine-Westphalian (NRW) universities, we also host another ELN software at the ZIM, the open-source solution "eLabFTW", see "Fig. 2". In addition, we have set up a NRW-wide working group[2] to explore the needs of researchers and to promote the joint cooperation of the infrastructure facilities so as to jointly establish an action recommendation for researchers. We deliberately chose generic ELN software because it can be used more widely; "Table 1" shows a brief comparison of different ELN applications.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the Software eLabFTW

Table 1. Comparison of commercial and open-source ELN solutions

	Name	Licence	Features
1	labfolder	free, academic, industry	usually cloud-based; supports both teaching and learning, variety of collaboration tools, ISO certified Labs, integration for dropbox, figshare and with labfolder API
2	RSpace	community, academic, industry	generic, supports all disciplines, connection to filesystems (linking data from inside the ELN), chemical editor, calculator, integration of communication tools (slack, hangouts etc), many export formats
3	LabArchives	free, academic, other	cloud-based; additional classroom edition: 2.200+ instructors, 5.700+ courses, 317.000+ student notebooks, 6.500+ trees saved
4	eLabFTW	open-source	selfhosted serverinstallation with docker, import/export functions for common fileformats, templates, molecule drawer, for all possible team sizes; strong encryption, responsive design, cross-platform, supports timestamps, inventory management
5	Jupyter	open-source	web application notebook to create and share documents, for programming code, equations, visualizations etc
6	chemotion	open-source	specific ELN for chemistry, funded by DFG, additional chemistry repository for research data (with DOI integration), Spectra Viewer, ChemScanner

2.1 Requirements for ELN

The laboratory work should be well structured and documented. At the same time, researchers also want to be able to quickly file information in an unstructured area, especially in the active practical phase, in order to document it cleanly in the follow-up work[3].

So the user side puts different kinds of requirements on an ELN. In addition to the technical requirements such as user-friendliness, the use of known file formats and the constant digital availability of the data, there is also a desire for the possibility to completely remove the data from the ELN software and continue working elsewhere. So-called "exit strategies" have to be reconsidered before starting work with digital (web) tools, otherwise a later change can become costly and unpleasant[3]. Researchers who are already working with ELNs are also asking for an offline version, since the internet connection of the laboratories is often not guaranteed to a sufficient extent.

Regarding the regulatory requirements, especially for externally funded projects, the adherence to good scientific practice and good laboratory practice is in the foreground. This includes the secure storage of research data, as well as ensuring the availability and findability of these. When publishing, a digital transfer should be considered directly in a research data repository in which the data can be permanently retrieved using a digital object identifier (DOI).

In addition, there are specific technical requirements, which may differ greatly under certain circumstances. While the chemists use a special molecular drawing editor and also want to search for such formulas within the ELN, for example, physicists or engineers need an interface to Matlab in order to be able to link and/or display the measurement/raw data directly in the ELN. In order to get a better overview, the AG ELB.NRW[2] invited several researchers from different fields to talk about their requirements, see "Table 2".

*Table 2. Presentation of the current ELN situation of invited researchers
(using an interview guideline)*

	Area of Expertise	Status ELN	Operation Area
1	Exp. Medical Physics	uses elabFTW	Research
2	Biochemical Plant Physiology	uses elabFTW	Research
3	Neurobiology	tests elabFTW	Research & Teaching
4	Neuropathology, medicine	tests elabFTW	Research
5	Neurosurgery, medicine	tests elabFTW	Research
6	Cardiology, medicine	tests elabFTW	Research
7	Molekular Enzyme Technology	uses elabFTW	Research
8	Phoniatics & Paediatric Audiology, medicine	interested in ELN	Teaching
9	Photosynthesis and Stress Physiology of Plants	interested in ELN	Teaching
10	Organic Photochemistry	interested in ELN	Teaching

2.2 Usecases

Research group leaders who are already confident in the digital environment of their discipline are quick to enjoy using an ELN. They instruct their employees and after a short time all work together digitally within a self-defined framework in the laboratory. Other researchers have less technical experience, but are still open to the new direction and want basic training on ELNs and specific software recommendations. But at the same time the electronic version can also be used in parallel with the tried and tested paper laboratory book. Researchers report that employees who are very used to a workflow would not change without a service instruction. Better would be an early notice of the matter, such as the use of electronic laboratory books yet during the first use of the laboratory: So already in the teaching.

3 RESULTS

Through various consultations in the field of research data management, we noticed at the HHU that many researchers from different fields, be it biology, chemistry, physics or medicine, are not sufficiently informed as far as the topic of electronic laboratory work is concerned. The biology would like to see an easier handling of the 300 students who have to complete a specific course in plant physiology in the third semester. In neurobiology, Master's students can learn the first steps in electronic fluorometry imaging labs (how to generate and interpret data in this area). Also in medicine, for example in the field of neurosurgery or neuropathology, many lecturers are interested in the idea of using ELNs in teaching. The student's theses are mostly submitted digitally; in addition, there is often additional unstructured and poorly searchable documentation that does not become part of the thesis. The passing on of methods and know-how is important to lecturers. The size of the laboratory also plays a role, because the larger the laboratory, the more complex the organisation of laboratory documentation becomes.

The development of the digitization of laboratory documentation can be seen as a maturity process and only after a certain degree of systematization is an introduction of ELN in teaching recommended. From maturity level II, see "Fig. 3", the documentation process for laboratory work is systematically structured and can be repeated in consistent quality. The feedback of experienced researchers on the use of ELN in laboratory practice, as well as the early introduction of students to a systematic scientific approach in the documentation of laboratory experiments is a good combination of research and teaching. With the introduction of ELN and the systematization of the laboratory documentation, this degree of maturity and thus these advantages can also be achieved for laboratory practicals in teaching.

Figure 3. In the style of the capability maturity model (CMM)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the field of fairly short laboratory internships, whether individual or group internships, the ELN can serve as a constant aid in the most diverse models of division of labor. In addition to online tests and video tutorials, working with the aid of the electronic lab book can be explained in order to prepare the students for the experimental phases independently. For example, the laboratory test can be prepared with suitable templates to optimize the activity in the laboratory [4]. In the presence phase, the laboratory test can be documented directly in the ELN and serve as a delivery protocol. As a conclusion, we first develop basic training materials in close cooperation with the teachers and individually address the didactic concept of the event. Students can get first impressions of the software either in advance or directly at the beginning of the planned event in which the work with electronic laboratory books is to be introduced.

Like an e-portfolio, ELN can be considered as a "collection of work results that can be combined with comments from tutors, teachers and fellow students, feedback opportunities, and personal reflections" [5] for the preparation and editing of laboratory experiments and use in teaching. Also like e-portfolios, ELNs can contain various electronic documents (most measurement data, tables, databases, screens or graphic evaluations), which can be available in different file formats and display modes. These analogies provide similar benefits for students who document their laboratory tests in ELN as well as for learners who design their e-portfolio:

- Development: The ELN reflects the personal development through the documentation of the various laboratory experiments presented.
- Presentation of the laboratory experiment and feedback: The presentation of the laboratory work can be shared and discussed with others; the documentation of your own laboratory tests can be used for your own further development.
- Group work: ELN can be used in the preparation, execution and analysis of group experiments; such group work can be evaluated.
- Grading: The ELN can be evaluated as protocol of the experiment as well.

These benefits of working with ELN require a level of maturity that provides students with a systematic and well-structured learning environment within the ELN platform that can also work on contiguous, consecutive lab practices in a defined consistent quality. First, introductory videos are planned as modular components for the use of the ELN software "eLabFTW". After that, depending on the event, we will create a team within this software and establish the basic requirements for starting the lab internship. An example is the plant physiology. It is planned to use templates to customize a baseline of the results protocol several times in different ways to provide a consistent format of protocol for up to ten instructors. The participating students should be able to read all protocols. With the introduction of ELN in teaching we hope for a faster and wider acceptance of the electronic laboratory books in order to optimize the research work in the laboratory and to advance the digitization there. We believe that ELNs are an excellent opportunity to be introduced to research activities and approaches at an early stage in teaching and to offer potential for independent learning in individual or group work in the laboratory.

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